

Downloading DHS Datasets

Template instructions which can be included in README files that describe re-using DHS data.

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Go to the DHS program website at thedhsprogram.com and register as a new user for data access

Login or Register for Datasets

New Users Register

Before you can download datasets, you must register as a DHS data user. Dataset access is only granted for legitimate research purposes. Learn more about data restrictions, [why we require registration](#), [how to request access](#) or view a [list of available datasets](#).

Please be aware that re-distribution of any DHS micro-level data, either directly or within any tool/dashboard, is not permitted.

[Register for Dataset Access](#)

Model Datasets Available

If you would like to try out some data files we have provided some example model datasets for which you do not need to register.

[Click here to download model dataset files.](#)

You have to justify the usage for requesting the data access. Here is a sample text to use:

This access is requested for data replication process for accepted paper on [TITLE] by [AUTHORS]. The analysis for the paper was carried out with DHS datasets under project title: [PROJECT TITLE].

In this project, the authors had requested the access for the following tasks:

[ORIGINAL ABSTRACT]

As the paper has been completed and accepted for publication by the [Journal], we are requesting access to check the data analysis process using replication codes submitted by the authors of the paper before publishing the paper. The access shall be used only for academic research purposes.

Once you are registered for data access, use the following selections in the DHS data downloading process to download the relevant data pertaining to this specific project:

Logged in: ss5910@columbia.edu

Download Datasets Using a Download Manager
Project: Health Insurance in Low-Income Countries

Select countries, file data types and file format then click "Build URL File List" button.

<p>Country</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Check/Uncheck All <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Afghanistan <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Albania <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Angola <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Armenia <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Azerbaijan <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bangladesh <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Benin <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bolivia <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brazil <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Burkina Faso <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Burundi <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cambodia <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cameroon <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Central African Republic <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Chad <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Colombia <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Comoros <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Congo 	<p>File Data Type *</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Check/Uncheck All (DHS) <p>DHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Births Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Children's Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Couples' Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Height and Weight Scores - WHO Child Growth Standards <input type="checkbox"/> Household Member Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Household Raw <input type="checkbox"/> Household Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Individual Raw <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Individual Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Men's Raw <input type="checkbox"/> Men's Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Other Data <input type="checkbox"/> Service Availability Raw <input type="checkbox"/> Verbal Autopsy <input type="checkbox"/> Village Recode <input type="checkbox"/> Wealth Index 	<p>File Format *</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Hierarchical <input type="checkbox"/> Flat file <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stata System file <input type="checkbox"/> SAS System file <input type="checkbox"/> SPSS System file <p>Surveys</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> All <input checked="" type="radio"/> All DHS <input type="radio"/> All SPA <input type="radio"/> All AIS <input type="radio"/> All MIS <input type="radio"/> Most Recent <input type="radio"/> Most Recent DHS <input type="radio"/> Most Recent SPA <input type="radio"/> Most Recent AIS <input type="radio"/> Most Recent MIS
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Click on the 'Build URL File List' button and wait a few minutes. The link to download the data will show up at the top like shown below:

Logged in: ss5910@columbia.edu

Download Datasets Using a Download Manager
Project: Health Insurance in Low-Income Countries

Click link below to view list of URLs or right click to download. Copy and paste or import the list into your download manager. There are various download managers available for all the major browsers. See [DHS Userforum](#) for more information.

- [Text file with URLs \(323 files\)](#)

Select countries, file data types and file format then click "Build URL File List" button.

Click on the 'Text file with URLs' then you will see a list of URLs:

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← → ↻ dhsprogram.com/data/download/urllist_157643.txt
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=AFIR71DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AF&surv_id=471&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=ALIR51DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AL&surv_id=327&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=ALIR71DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AL&surv_id=525&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=AOIR71DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AO&surv_id=477&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=AMIR42DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AM&surv_id=203&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=AMIR54DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AM&surv_id=262&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=AMIR61DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AM&surv_id=354&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=AMIR72DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AM&surv_id=492&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=AZIR52DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=AZ&surv_id=279&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR31DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=59&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR3ADT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=89&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR41DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=135&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR4JDT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=236&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR51DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=287&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR61DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=349&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR72DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=461&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BDIR7RDT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BD&surv_id=536&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BJIR31DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BJ&surv_id=87&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BJIR41DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BJ&surv_id=211&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BJIR51DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BJ&surv_id=289&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BJIR61DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BJ&surv_id=420&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BJIR71DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BJ&surv_id=491&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BOIR01DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BO&surv_id=28&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BOIR31DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BO&surv_id=65&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BOIR3BDT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BO&surv_id=98&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BOIR41DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BO&surv_id=238&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BOIR51DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BO&surv_id=319&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BRIR01DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BR&surv_id=2&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BRIR21DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BR&surv_id=40&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BRIR31DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BR&surv_id=85&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BFIR21DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BF&surv_id=42&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BFIR31DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BF&surv_id=116&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BFIR43DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BF&surv_id=230&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BFIR62DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BF&surv_id=329&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BUIR02DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BU&surv_id=16&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BUIR61DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BU&surv_id=346&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=BUIR71DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=BU&surv_id=463&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=KHIR42DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=KH&surv_id=140&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=KHIR51DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=KH&surv_id=257&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=KHIR61DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=KH&surv_id=310&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=KHIR73DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=KH&surv_id=464&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=CMIR22DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=CM&surv_id=38&dm=1&dmode=nn
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=CMIR31DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=CM&surv_id=101&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=CMIR44DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=CM&surv_id=232&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=CMIR61DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=CM&surv_id=337&dm=1&dmode=r
https://dhsprogram.com/customcf/legacy/data/download_dataset.cfm?Filename=CMIR71DT.zip&Tp=1&Ctry_Code=CM&surv_id=511&dm=1&dmode=r
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Copy and paste or import the list into your download manager. The Research Analyst for this project used 'Simple Mass Downloader'. Here are the instructions on how this setup works:

The DHS Program datasets download system allows for bulk downloading to assist those users who are approved for a large number of countries/datasets. To use the bulk downloading system, data users must first install a download manager, which, due to authentication requirements, MUST be an extension or a plugin to a browser. There are a number of download managers available for each of the major browsers. We had been recommending an extension called "Chrono Download Manager" for the Google Chrome browser but this extension is no longer available from the Chrome library of extensions. There is a new extension called "Simple Mass Downloader" that is now available and works in a similar manner. Follow these steps to install the "Simple Mass Downloader" for Chrome:

- Open Chrome browser and go to this link: <https://chrome.google.com/webstore/detail/simple-mass-downloader/abdckegmcbiomjicbdaofaghehffed?hl=en-US>
- Click on the "Add to Chrome" button.
- It will ask "Add Simple mass downloader?". click the "Add extension" button.
- The extension should automatically install and a page will display with general instructions and other information.
- Make sure to take note of the advice/warning in the "red box" about making sure the "ask where to save.." check box is not checked.
- There should now be a small blue down arrow button near the top right of the Chrome browser.
- Click on that and the Simple Mass Downloader interface should appear. If it appears then the extension was installed correctly.
- Click it again to close it.

Now you need to login to your datasets account on the DHS Program website and follow these steps (these steps are for users of the "Simple Mass Downloader" extension):

- o After login, select a project.
- o Click on the "Download Manager" button.
- o Select countries, file data type, and file format type.
- o Click the "Build URL File list" button.
- o Just above your selections, there will be a link that says "Text file with URLs".
- o Click that link and a new tab should open with the list of URLs for the datasets from your selection.
- o Click again on the blue down arrow button at the top right to bring up the Simple Mass Downloader interface.
- o Click on the "Load Page Links" icon near the top left of the interface.
- o That should load all the URL links on the page into the Simple Mass Downloader interface. (NOTE: you must have the browser tab open with the list of URLs for this to work)
- o Click on the check box to the left of the "File Name" header. This will select all the files in the list.
- o Click on white down arrow near the bottom right of the interface.
- o The download process should start automatically.

Here is a sample image on how the chrome extension will look like and how to operate the mass downloader:

After clicking the download button, each country level zipfile will start downloading. These need to be added to the raw dataset folder path here: [YOUR REPLICATION FOLDER]

For more information see here:

<https://userforum.dhsprogram.com/index.php?t=msg&th=5246&start=0&S=4a22c1574b54935d933d662d79e0eaf2>

After downloading the zipfiles check the following information:

- [add checks here]